

THE ROLE OF MARKETING IN THE DEVELOPMENT AND POPULARIZATION OF FOOTBALL

Tulyaganov Akmal Axmadovich

UzDJTSU "Football Theory and Methodology"
department etc. associate professor, pedagogical sciences
Doctor of Philosophy (PhD).

Javlon Esanov

Uzbekistan State University of Physical Education and Sports
Department of management and organization of sports events
Direction of sports marketing.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14220280>

Abstract. This article examines the significant role that marketing has played in the transformation of football from a regional sport to a global phenomenon. It delves into the key marketing strategies employed by clubs, leagues, and governing bodies to build brand identity, expand reach, promote player development, drive revenue, and foster positive social impact. The article concludes by highlighting the enduring influence of marketing on the sport's trajectory and its continued relevance in a rapidly evolving global landscape.

Keywords: Football, Marketing, Brand Identity, Fan Engagement, Global Reach, Player Development, Revenue Generation, Social Impact, Sports Industry.

FUTBOLNING RIVOJLANISHIDA HAMDA OMMAVIYLASHISHIDA MARKETINGNING O'RNI

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada marketing futbolning mintaqaviy sport turidan global hodisaga aylanishida qanday muhim rol o'ynaganini ko'rib chiqadi. U klublar, ligalar va boshqaruv organlari tomonidan brend identifikatorini shakllantirish, ta'sir doirasini kengaytirish, o'yinchilarni rivojlantirish, daromadlarni oshirish va ijobiy ijtimoiy ta'sirni kuchaytirish uchun qo'llaniladigan asosiy marketing strategiyalarini o'rganadi. Maqolaning yakunida marketingning sport traektoriyasiga doimiy ta'siri va uning tez rivojlanayotgan global landshaftdagi dolzarbligi ta'kidlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: Futbol, marketing, brend identifikatori, muxlislar ishtiroki, global ta'sir, o'yinchilarni rivojlantirish, daromad olish, ijtimoiy ta'sir, sport sanoti.

Introduction

Introduction Football, often called soccer in some parts of the world, has transcended its origins as a regional pastime to become a globally adored sport. This evolution can be attributed in no small part to the strategic application of marketing principles. From building brand identity and fostering fan loyalty to expanding global reach and driving revenue, marketing has played a pivotal role in shaping the modern football landscape. This article delves into the diverse ways in which marketing has propelled football's development and popularization, exploring its impact on the sport's economic, social, and cultural fabric.

In the dynamic world of sports, marketing in football plays an essential role in promoting and managing the brand image of both clubs and international tournaments. Through effective marketing strategies, organizations can increase their visibility, enhance their reputation, and deeply connect with fans around the world.

Methods

Around the world, early football is evident in many locations. The Modern football, which originated in England in the late nineteenth century, can be thought of as an ancestor of the game that civilisations played throughout history. Football was played in ancient cultures as early as 2500 BC, according to some evidence. But their motivations varied; some associated football with religious rituals, while others recognised qualities that could aid in enhancing military tactics [1].

Football was mostly a loss-making sport before to the 1980s since it was not entirely integrated into commercial operations and was isolated from business. To just enjoy playing the game and competing, friends and coworkers started the first football teams. At that time, football was only for entertainment and players were playing without any commercial interest [2].

The phrase "sports marketing," which describes the connection between marketing and sports, has entered common usage. According to one definition, the word refers to a collection of marketing initiatives that are solely focused on sports and the consumer who anticipates services associated to sports [3]. Three categories of marketing activity can be identified within this category: 1) marketing of sports goods and services that emphasises encouraging consumers to attend various sporting events; 2) marketing that does not specifically promote sports goods but instead makes use of associations with sports; and 3) marketing to advertise a sports organisation in order to draw viewers and encourage businesses to support the organisation financially (Michalek, b.d.). The first step in developing a sports club's image is generating a specific identity of the brand in the mind of the fan (consumer).

Lindstrom made a bold claim when he discovered similarities between religious organisations and sports in terms of projecting an emotional image. The author lists these planes as follows: majesty (club exclusivity, elitism); myths and legends (achievements, traditions); a sense of belonging (common attire, singing); a unifying common enemy (opposing club); recommendation (endorsing a club, athlete, or event); symbols (club logo, colours, symbolic players); and rituals (songs, hymns).

These elements serve as the foundation for creating a sports club's identity in a way that makes it clearly and accurately identifiable [4].

Results and discussion

Numerous clubs were established in this way as a result of the professional game's inevitable appeal to businesspeople who wanted to use it as a means of making money. The phrase "football business" first appeared in the early 1990s as a result of business ventures in the sector.

Without a question, football has changed and is now a major industry rather than just a sport. Since new opportunities are emerging, wise decisions are needed. As with every business, marketing plays a critical part in the growth of the football industry.

Marketing for Football Clubs

Football clubs have millions of fans worldwide and are more than just sports teams. Football clubs utilise marketing to increase fan loyalty, make money from sponsorships and retail sales, and establish their brand globally. In order to engage with supporters and keep the club relevant both during and outside of the season, tactics including producing original content, running social media campaigns, and holding brand activations are essential.

Clubs like Real Sociedad use their mascot on social media, while Leganés is known for creative advertisements. Manchester City has launched a TikTok account specifically for the American market, expanding its reach. FC Barcelona uses immersive experiences and AR technology globally, and Juventus promotes documentaries on streaming platforms, strengthening the emotional bond with fans.

Marketing in World Cups and International Competitions

Global competitions such as the FIFA World Cup provide enormous opportunities for sports advertising. Here, the main goals are to maximise worldwide visibility, draw in well-known sponsors, and provide fans experiences they won't soon forget. In addition to capturing the thrill of the occasion, marketing efforts for these contests need to develop a story that appeals to viewers around the world and in many cultural contexts. To accomplish these goals, technology, narrative, and social media interaction are essential instruments.

References

1. <https://business-school.laliga.com/en/news/marketing-in-the-world-of-football-clubs-tournaments>
2. D. Conn, *The Football Business: Fair Game in the '90s?*, Edinburgh: Mainstream publishing 1999, pp. 41
3. Sznajder, A. (2008). *Marketing sportu*. Warszawa: Polskie Wydawnictwo Ekonomiczne
4. Rak, A. (2012). Kreowanie marki w sporcie. *Zeszyty Naukowe Uniwersytetu Szczecińskiego. Problemy Zarządzania, Finansów i Marketingu*, (20), 173–181.
5. Świtała, M. & Kieźel, M. (2017). E-narzędzia oraz przyszłość marketingu w działalności usługodawców logistycznych – wyniki badań. *Studia Ekonomiczne. Zeszyty Naukowe Uniwersytetu Ekonomicznego w Katowicach*, (321), 100–117. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/320004054_E-NARZEDZIA_ORAZ_PRZYSZLOSC_MARKETINGU_W_DZIALALNOSCI_USLU_GODAWCOW_LOGISTYCZNYCH_-_WYNIKI_BADAN
6. Iglesias, G. (2021). *The influence of social media in sport marketing*. Marbella International University Centre. Retrieved April 3, 2022 from <https://miuc.org/influence-social-mediasport-marketing>.